

ANALYSIS OF THE QUANTITY OF POISONOUS GASES EMITTED FROM VEHICLES OF TRANSPORTATION.

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Currently, as a result of the sharp increase in the number of vehicles in our region, the amount of toxic gases emitted by vehicles is destroying the ecological environment of our region. In contrast to stationary sources, pollutants emitted from the motor vehicle complex accumulate in the upper layer of the atmosphere, directly in the breathing region. This leads to the accumulation of lead compounds and other toxic, carcinogenic substances in the human body, causing its health to deteriorate. Harmful to the atmospheric air of the vehicle complex causes serious problems that are urgently needed:

- widespread use of ethylated gasoline and high-sulfur diesel fuel, while the quality of motor fuel does not meet the requirements;

- the wear and tear of motor vehicles in need of repair is the reason for the increase of harmful waste;

- in the enterprises of the republic, the diagnostic bases are underdeveloped, there are few devices for controlling fuel quality, the lack of devices for controlling the level of toxicity and pollution of gases coming out of engines is very noticeable;

- the transfer of motor vehicles to natural compressed and liquefied petroleum gas is being carried out very slowly, today on average 20-25% of vehicles are gasified in the republic [1].

Currently, the number of cars in our region is given in the table below. 140,480 motor vehicles were registered in the region, of which the number of vehicles in the private sector is 122,967, and the number of vehicles in the public sector is 17,521 [2].

Viloyat boyicha jami ro'yhatdan o'tgan transport vositalari soni

The table below shows the indicators of cars with carburetor, diesel engine and gas cylinder. As can be seen from the histogram, there are 11,778 carbureted vehicles in the region, of which 107,400 are in the private sector, and 10,331 are in the public sector [3].

Davlat ro'yhatidan o'tgan transport vositalari soni

If we look at our histogram below, it shows the movement of the number of carbureted, diesel and gas cylinder cars [4].

Karbyuratorli transport vositalari soni

Dizell davigatelli transport vositalari soni

Gaz balon o`rnatilgan transport vositalari soni

If we look at the following histogram, if we analyze the polluting substances coming out of the motor vehicle complex in our region for the years 2022-2023, it can be observed that the most amount of toxic gases in the upper layer of the atmosphere is in the city of Andijan [5].

Andijon viloyati bo'yicha transport vositalaridan chiqayotgan zaharli gazlarning miqdori

In the next places, it was observed in Kurgantepa, Shahrikhan and Khodjaabad districts. We can observe the lowest rate in Boz and Ulug'nor districts, one of the remote areas of our region [7].

In order to prevent this situation and as a result of not polluting the environment, it would be desirable to achieve the following:

- to ensure that the quality of motor fuel meets the requirements of GOST, to avoid using ethylated gasoline and diesel fuel with a high level of sulfur;
- timely control of vehicle engine repairs and reduction of harmful waste;
- to dramatically increase and develop diagnostic bases in regional enterprises, to achieve an increase in the set of devices that control fuel quality;
- it is necessary to increase the number of devices that control the level of toxicity and pollution of gases coming out of engines;
- to increase the transfer of motor vehicles to natural compressed and liquefied gases;
- all vehicles in the province should be passed through the laboratory from the department of ecology [8].

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